

Dissemination of Quality Knowledge for Educational, Community and National Development: Our Inaugural Editorial Statement

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Abstract

This is an editorial statement for the Journal of Education Research and Rural Community Development (JERRCD); the journal is releasing its inaugural publication. The article provided a brief background to the journal, and the research forum that birthed the Journal was situated, coupled with its meritorious promises for quality knowledge production. The reviews and the review processes, the

ethical issues considering the operation of the journal was itemised with request for adequate compliance by the contributors (authors). In order to describe the compendium of originality and quality production, the article also described the calibre of pioneering scholars that constitute the editorial board. The article conclusively described its modus operandi as second to none with an affirmative recommendation for well-meaning scholars to partner with us in the journey.

Key words: Quality Knowledge, Community development, Educational development, National development.

Introduction

Education in the 21st century is provocative, most especially when it comes to knowledge production and dissemination to the wider world (Jones, 2016; Shay, 2017). It bothers more on the assertion that “knowledge is power”. This epistemologically aged adage could only be made whole when the produced knowledge is indiscriminately disseminated to those who require it. The predatory practices currently experiencing in the world of academic publishing today has shown contrary to the quality of knowledge dissemination needed for inter/transdisciplinary knowledge development. This is evidenced in the testimonies of Richtig, Berger, Lange-Asschenfeldt, Aberer & Richtig (2018) that the world is full of journals without any iota of quality in the input, process, and output of their publication. These unethical practices according to Olijhoek & Tennant (2018) should not be allowed to thrive and contaminate the qualities of the quality producers. Therefore, the onus is upon us to join the rest of the academic communities across the world in remaking the world with quality production of knowledge and by rethinking education for inclusive development.

Our journal, **Journal of Education Research and Rural Community Development (JERRCD)**, is set predominantly for knowledge production, that is, we are bent on entertaining quality research outputs in general education with quintessential focus on emancipation, re-memberment and remaking of the rural people, the community and its developmental praxis along with the trajectory of its education system through freely dissemination of quality researchers' outputs that could transcend to all-round development. This becomes important because literature had demonstrated from the global south that rurality, community, and their education system are suffering from the rampant marginalisation, lack and insufficient resources, bad and inconsistent policy implementation, among others (Stelmach, 2011; SayedI & Badroodien, 2016; Omodan & Dube, 2019). Consequent upon these, the **Journal of Education Research and Rural Community Development** is stationed to respond to the aforementioned challenges in the cross-disciplinary, trans-disciplinary and multi-disciplinary education space.

This Journal is birthed by *Education Research and Rural Community Development Forum* in 2019. The forum is a registered community of scholars membered by researches across the world with focus on revitalisation of *Education Research and Rural Community Development*, aims to fashion out a way forward to the discrepancies in the rural education and community development ranging from the disparities in inclusive education for social justice, resource allocation to rural communities, and rural located schools (primary, secondary and higher education) amongst others. Apart from these, the forum researches and provides services on general education space, leadership and management, policy formulation and implementation, creation and managing educational organisations such as schools. Among other focuses are training and retraining on teaching and learning, education and community leadership, research and development for individual, group of individuals, schools and any other educational and community-related institutions.

The forum with its advisory board agreed that the journal should be "open access" targeted towards rethinking Education for inclusive Development. And that articles should seek to provide either empirical, conceptual, or theoretical opinions on current educational and community-related issues. It also encourages discourse on interdisciplinary, cross-disciplinary and transdisciplinary education and community development-related issues, policies and practices. In addition, the

journal is also interested in thought-provoking and intellectual debates on general education issues affecting primary, secondary, higher education and even nations in the global perspective.

JERRCD Review and the Review Process

Perceptions exist among scholars that biases and halo-effect characterized many journals' review process and has posed negative effects on the quality of blind peer review process, this in the assumption of Lee, Sugimoto, Zhang, & Cronin, (2013) is that nationality, location, gender, race among others influences manuscripts assessment process by both the editors and the reviewers due to a probably preconceived halo-effect. This is also supported by Murray et al., (2018), that Editors and reviewers may also develop a soft landing for the authors whose work regionally appeal to him/her either by language or nationality. Contrary to the above, our journal has devised a technical means to ensure a workflow system of review that disengages the identity of author from the reviewers and vis-versa. That is, JERRCD uses double-blind review system designed by Open Journal System (OJS) and Public Knowledge Project (PKP) where both the reviewers' and the authors' identities are restricted from each other from the beginning (submission stage) to the output (publication state) but made transparent to the participants. In order to implement this, authors are the principal players by ensuring that all manuscripts are prepared in such a way that disallows the use of any word, phrase and or statement that could expose the authors' identities. This includes names, affiliations, funders' name and address, and acknowledgment among others. On the other hand, our reviewers under no circumstance(s) will use any derogatory words to address, debase and reject any submitted manuscript. (See Author Guidelines JERRCD).

Ethical Issue of JERRCD

The *Journal of Education Research and Rural Community Development* encourages ethical standard of research aesthetic by not jettisoning respect for justices, accuracy, respect for personal, racial, religious gender, language, and other differences. This is to say, that our journal only welcome articles that promote peace, respect, recognition, social justices for people, their community and their peculiar educational system that contribute to people's and organisational sustainability and epistemic development. Our ethical consideration further includes an assurance that the manuscript has not been published, submitted or sent for consideration elsewhere. Proof

of language editing done by native/L1 language speakers or experts in English Language is required and that only zero levels of plagiarism are allowed. In the case of research/project that involves minors, we encourage the authors to produce ethical clearance from relevant authorities and or project director/coordinator/president as the case may be. The following are the important few of our ethical guidelines;

1. All cited authors in the in-text must be adequately referenced in the article, the article (tables, figures, referencing and citation style) must strictly adhere to American Psychological Association (APA). The in-text citations and reference list in this article is a perfect example. See www.jerrcd.org (Author Guidelines) for more information.
2. Copyright issues, rules, and regulations must be respected.
3. Authors should desist from using derogatory words or statements about one group, race, nationality, gender and language or a claim of superiority as the case may be.
4. Professionalism in dealing with samples/co-researchers/participants in research process by respecting the right of samples/co-researchers /participants to either or not participate must be considered.
5. The author must declare in a statement showing that the article has only been sent for consideration in JERRCD and will not be sent for consideration elsewhere except our team decide otherwise.

Describing our Editorial Team

In order to maintain the paradigm of quality knowledge production, our journal has deemed it fit to parade the best editorial team any journal can dream of. Our team comprises of renowned researchers from all spares of educational, social and community-related fields of studies. Among us are many scholars who are currently making wave in their field with many of them recognized and rated as a result of scholarships engagements, project and funding from various government and non-governmental organization, all of us are members of one of two education and research organizations. Not only that, the composition of our team is a dream for many journals but for us, the expected international standard for the composition of editorial team is met without jettisoning intellectual standard. With this and many more, we can say boldly that our team unambiguously comprised of international scholarly practices that are set to discharge radical and revolutionary publications for the world use. The following are the profiles of our team:

Profiling Our Editorial Team

1. **Prof Bulent Tarman**, *Gazi University, Turkey*

Bulent Tarman has more than 23 years of professional experience in the field of education including teaching, training, planning, programming, monitoring and evaluation of projects. He earned his Ph.D. in Curriculum & Instruction (social studies education), as well as a minor in Comparative and International Education, from the Penn State University in the USA. He also holds a BA in history (Hacettepe University) and MEd in social studies education (University of Missouri, Columbia). He has worked as an Associate Professor at the Faculty of Education and Deputy Chair & EU Project Unit Coordinator of Project Coordination Implementation and Research Center at Gazi University in Ankara Turkey. Prof. Tarman is also Editor-in-Chief of the Journal of Social Studies Education Research. His research interests include Social Studies Education; Teacher Education; Innovation in Education; Citizenship and Human Rights Education, Globalizing Education, Curriculum Development; Gender Issues in Education; ICT in Education; and Multiculturalism in Education.

2. **Prof Mariette Koen**, *North-West University, South Africa*

Prof Mariëtte Koen is an associate professor and lecturer in the School of Psycho-Social Education, Faculty of Education, North-West University, Potchefstroom, South Africa. She is a recipient of four Dean's medals (1985, 1986, 1998, 1999), and was nominated for The HELTASA Excellence in Teaching and Learning Award (2013). She started her career as a remedial and foundation phase school teacher before she obtained a professional qualification as an Educational Psychologist. Her doctorate is in the area of reading and spelling development and she obtained a Masters in Philosophy in Higher Education at Stellenbosch University 2011. She is a member of the COMBER research niche (NWU) and is currently researching community engagement in ECD.

3. **Prof Akin Ogunlade**, *AU Washington, United States*

Prof Akinlolu Lucas OGUNLADE (B.Sc OAU Ife, M.Ed Howard University, Ph.D. AU Washington) taught at Howard University and George Washington University, University of Port Harcourt, University of Ilorin, and Ekiti state University until mandatory retirement at age 70. He was appointed as the Vice Chancellor of Ekiti State University of Education. Also was Director of Advancement Directorate at Ekiti State University. He was Head of Department of Educational Management at the University of Ilorin, Regular Educational Policy Analyst on State Television

networks. He was a Post-Doctoral fellow, George Washington University. He lectured and conducted researches in several education planning, policy, administration and legal issues in education. He supervised 38 Ph.D theses and 67 Masters Dissertations. External Examiner for Ph.D at the OAU Ife, Universities of Ibadan, Benin, Ilorin and also assessor for Professorships in the aforementioned Universities. Prof Ogunlade is Editor in Chief of several reputable academic international journals. He is a fellow and member of several prominent international professional organizations and recipient of several major international and local academic and community awards of excellence.

4. **Prof Emmanuel O. Adu**, *University of Fort Hare, South Africa*

Prof Emmanuel O. Adu is a Full Professor in the School of General and Continuing Education, Faculty of Education, University of Fort Hare, Republic of South Africa. He is a recipient of Faculty of Education, University of Fort Hare mentorship grant awards 2014-2017, Vice Chancellor Senior Research Medal Awards 2015 and 2017, faculty of education award of excellence 2015-2018 and recognition of service award by the School of General and Continuing Education (SGCE) 2015-2018. He has taught for over 20 years at universities in Nigeria, Botswana and South Africa. His research interests include; Economics education, Teacher education and development, Education Management, Curriculum studies, ICT in education, and educational research. He is a recipient of many international awards and editorial board member of many national and international referred journals. He has to his credit 170 articles in refereed journals, chapters in books and conference proceedings. He has supervised 105 Masters and 27 doctoral students.

5. **Prof Michael S. Omirin**, *Ekiti State University, Nigeria*

Prof. Michael Sunday OMIRIN is a full Professor of Tests and Measurement at the Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. He was Head of Department of the Department of Guidance and Counselling, and presently the Director of the Directorate of Continuing Education Programmes (DCEP) of Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti. He has published in both National and International journals. He also authors several books/monographs and Chapters-In-Books. He has supervised several Masters and Ph.D candidates. He is an External Examiner to some Universities like Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife; Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko; University

of Ibadan; Olabisi Onanbanjo University, Ago-Iwoye and others. He is also an assessor for Readerships and Professorships in the same Universities mentioned. Prof. Omirin is a member of many academic and professional organizations among which are; Mathematical Association of Nigeria; Science Association of Nigeria; Association of Educational Researchers and Evaluators of Nigeria (ASSEREN). His research and lecturing interests remain but not limited to; Research Method and Data Processing, Techniques in CRF and Continuous Assessment, Techniques of Achievement Analysis, Tests and Measurement–Educational and Psychological Testing, Vocational and Career Testing, Curriculum Evaluation, Statistical Method in Education, Educational and Psychological Testing, Advanced Observational Techniques, Advanced Research Methods in Education among others.

6. **Prof Rosa Branca Tracana**, *Institute Polytechnic of Guarda, Portugal*

Prof Rosa Branca Tracana is a Professor in School of Education, Sports and Communication of Polytechnic of Guarda, Portugal. Her teaching career is dated back to 1996 in the area of science education. She had graduated several masters and Ph.D students and had published many international and local articles with not less than 9 chapters in international book. She participated in several international projects. Her research interests include Science Education, Environmental Education, Teacher Education, Educational research.

7. **Prof Haastrup T. Ekundayo**, *Ekiti State University, Nigeria*

Haastrup Ekundayo is an Associate Professor of Educational Management and Administration in the Department of Educational Management, Ekiti State University Nigeria. He holds BSc.Ed in Economics; M.Ed in Educational Management and Ph.D in Educational Management. He has been lecturing over 14 years in the university system. He had supervised a reasonable number of projects, 10 Masters Dissertations and 4 Ph.D. thesis (ongoing). He was once the secretary of Postgraduate committee Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University. He has been the managing editor of various books of reading and currently he is the managing editor of International Journal of Educational Foundations and Management. And Contemporary Issues in Education. Both journals are domiciled in the Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University. Dr Haastrup Ekundayo has authored 10 Books, 12 Chapters-in-Books. In his continuous contribution to academic development has published over 85 articles in learned journals across the world. His research

areas include but not limited to Economics of Education, educational management, leadership, policy studies, Education Law and research methodology.

8. **Dr Cias T. Tsotetsi**, *University of the Free State, South Africa*

Dr Cias Tsotetsi is the Assistant Dean and a lecturer in the Faculty of Education at the Qwaqwa Campus of the University of the Free State. He has been in the school environment for about 24 years. He joined the UFS in 2010 as a lecturer, the post he is currently occupying. Dr Tsotetsi's research has been on Critical Emancipatory Research, Participatory Action Research as well as Adaptive Leadership. Between the years 2013 and 2014, he has been part of a partnership between the UFS and the University of KwaZulu-Natal in a project funded by the National Research Foundation. He has published his work both nationally and internationally. Dr Tsotetsi has been a member of the Sustainable Rural Learning Ecologies/Sustainable Learning Environments colloquia for the past years. He has also served in the organization of other conferences. He has been instrumental in coordinating postgraduate activities and research on the Qwaqwa Campus of the University of the Free State. He led a sub-project on "contextually and culturally responsive education" under the umbrella of the Afromontane project.

9. **Dr Kamal Soomro**, *West Virginia University, United States*

Dr Kamal Soomro completed his doctorate in Education with emphasis in Instructional Design and Technology from West Virginia University, United States. He works as an Assistant Professor in the Institute of Business Management (IoBM) Karachi Pakistan. He is an Associate Editor of the Journal of Education and Educational Development (JoEED). Dr Soomro is on the review board of several other research journals in the field of education. He has also been associated with the Chicago School of Professional Psychology as an SME/Consultant for their online doctoral program in Educational Psychology and Technology. His research interests include investigations on the digital divide in educational settings and effective use of ICT to enhance teaching-learning process.

10. **Dr Folashade R. Ogunshola**, *National Open University of Nigeria*

Dr. Folashade Roseline Ogunshola, is a visiting lecturer, examiner, supervisor, and a researcher in the Department of Educational Foundations, National Open University of Nigeria. She holds

Ph.D in Educational Administration and Planning from University of Abuja. She has published in both national and international journals and chapters-in-Book. Her interest includes but not limited Educational Administration, Management, Planning, ICT in Education, Conflict Resolution and Peace Education among others. She has been a Reviewer for various publication houses including but not limited to African Academic Research Forum (AARF). She is a Fellow of the Institute of Management Consultants, Certified Management Consultant, member of the Nigeria Association for Educational Administration and Planning (NAEAP), Commonwealth Council for Educational Administration and Management (CCEAM) and Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN), among others.

11. Dr Olubukola C. Dada, Kwara State University, Nigeria

Dr Olubukola Christianah Dada is a Senior Lecturer in Department of Special Education, and the Director of Centre for Undergraduate Research, Kwara State University, Nigeria. She holds a doctorate in Special Education from the University of Ibadan. She is a recipient of the Best Student Award at the Senior Management Institute Training held at South Africa National Council for the Blind, Pretoria South Africa in 2012. Dr Olubukola is a member of many Professional Bodies such as National Association of Exceptional Children, Nigeria Association of Special Education Teachers (NASSET), Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN), American Association on Intellectual and Developmental and Kenya Association of Professional Counsellors amongst others. She has taught for over twenty years in Colleges of Education and Universities in Nigeria. She has presented several papers at scholarly conferences and workshops, both locally and internationally. She has authored books, chapters-in-book, and published in reputable local and international journals. Her research focus is not limited to special and gender education, human rights education, education and rehabilitation and diversity management.

12. Dr Olugbenga Ige, University of the Free State, South Africa

Dr Olugbenga Adedayo IGE (Ph.D) is a researcher and lecturer in the School of Social Sciences and Language Education, University of the Free State, Republic of South Africa. He has taught and conducted researches in education for more than eight years at universities in West and South Africa. He was one of the five recipients of the prestigious University of Ibadan Postgraduate Scholarship for 2009/2010 session, and the only African selected for the 2009/2010 Kaspersky IT

Security Conference for the Next Generation held in the United Kingdom and Poland respectively. Dr Olugbenga Ige was a Postdoctoral Research Fellow at the University of the Free State, South Africa. His academic outputs are not limited to project supervision, books, chapters-in-book, articles in reputable journals, among others. His research interests include but not limited Teacher Education, ICTs for Human Security, Social Studies Education, Civic Education, ICT in Education, Child and Youth Studies, Participatory Action Research, among others.

13. **Dr Tshele John Moloji** : *Sol Plaatje University, South Africa*

Dr Tshele Moloji, is Mathematics Education Senior lecturer in the Natural Science Teaching Department at Sol Plaatje University, RSA. He is part of the supervisory team, supervising the cohorts of Postgraduate students within the Sustainable Learning Environments-Sustainable Rural Learning Ecologies Research team (SULE/SuRLeC). Research interests are Mathematics in Contexts, Mathematics Education Curriculum, Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) in Mathematics Education. He also conducted Short Learning Programs for In-Service teachers on Mathematical Pedagogical Content Knowledge for the Free State Department of Education. Before joining the Teacher Education at higher institutions, he worked for 5 years as Mathematics Subject Advisor for Free State Department of Education.

14. **Dr Oluwaseyi Michael Oderinde**, *University of California San Diego, CA, USA*

Dr. Oluwaseyi M. Oderinde is a Research Fellow in the Department of Radiation Medicine and Applied Sciences, University of California San Diego and an Honorary Researcher/Adjunct Faculty in the School of Physics, University of Witwatersrand. He is a recipient of several academic merit awards. He has spent the past six years as a teacher and medical/radiation physics researcher. Dr. Oderinde has reviewed several articles for Scientific Journals and published his work in reputable Journals. His research interests are not limited to radiation science, physical science, and physics education.

15. **Dr Olubukola J. Ojo**, *University of Ilorin, Nigeria*

Dr Olubukola J. Ojo (Ph.D) is a lecturer and researcher with over eight years of research experience in the Department of Educational Management, University of Ilorin. He had supervised/supervising research Projects, theses and currently, he is the undergraduate coordinator of the Department of Educational Management. He had authored many academic publications such

as chapters-in-book, conference proceedings. He had published in both local and international journals. Besides, he is a member of the British Educational Leadership, Management and Administration Society (BELMAS), Nigerian Association of Educational Administration and Planning (NAEAP), Nigerian Institute of Management (NIM) among others His research interest includes but not limited to educational planning, management, economics and ICT Education.

Conclusion

From the above summary of our editorial highlight, you will agree with me that it is not an overstatement to affirmatively say that whatever comes out from us is nothing but the quality that could not be contested otherwise. This affirmation also deduced from the nature and the *modus operandi* of the journal, ranging from our editorial trustworthiness, transparency, honesty and criticality. Also, not limited to this, our review process is transparent, rigorous, critically and politely qualitative. This and many more is an indication that JERRCD is democratic, academic, considerate for originality and promptness prowess. However, we are confirming to authors and reader, and all well-meaning researchers that our product and conglomerate is second to none, therefore, we are here to serve the world in terms of quality knowledge production.

Recommendations

Based on the above, we are calling on all authors to trust us with your intellectual outputs. We will serve you well in all manners that are required to make your research readable and accessible all over the world. In doing this, you are enjoyed to respect the following; that concerted efforts should be made by all authors to remove all the indications of identity from their “Manuscripts” while submitting manuscripts to ensure blinded relationship between the author(s) and the reviewer(s). This step among others will be 100% considered before initiating the review process. These should;

- Prepare two different documents; the first document named "**main manuscript**" must only contain the title of the manuscript, the abstract and the entire article. The second document which must be named and uploaded as "**supplementary file**" must contain the title, author(s) information, abstract and the email address of the corresponding author.
- In case of the author(s) citing their previous works, the name(s) must be replaced with “author and year” in the text and also replicated in the references session instead of authors' name, article title, etc

- By naming your documents, author(s) identification should also be removed from the properties of the files, instead, name your main article with "**main manuscript**" and information file as "**supplementary file**".

In the same vein, manuscripts must be prepared with Microsoft Word in 1.5 spacing using a 12-point font in Times New Roman. You are advised to employ italics rather than underlining. Please note that figures, tables, and other graphics must be placed at the appropriate place within the text according to the authors' interest. The recommended length for manuscripts is between 3500 and 8000 words, including references, an abstract of 300 words or less, and any appendixes. In the case of multiple authors, the manuscript must indicate one author as the corresponding author.

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